
**Environmental Justice:
Making it a Reality for the Inuit Indigenous People in the Canadian
Arctic region**

A Policy Briefing

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Abstract

At the heart of this policy briefing is the issue of environmental justice.

“Inuit want to be involved in the future of the Arctic. We want to have meaningful consultation. We want to invest in our own future. We want a voice at the table because, after all, we are the people who will be living here ...” OKALIK EEGEESIAK, President Qikiqtani Inuit Association, Iqaluit, Nunavut (2011)

The Inuit Indigenous People in the Canadian Arctic (IIPCA), like many other indigenous people in other parts of Canada and world over, are victims of historical injustices resulting from colonization and dispossession of their land¹. While there is no one universal definition that encompasses the diversity of indigenous peoples², their common traditional way of life as well as the intimate connection to their environment sets them apart.

The relationship between the Canadian government and the Inuit indigenous people has been one shaped by a strained history, characterised by land grabs, and relocation and assimilation policies. As the country continues to face the legacy of this history and forge policies that encourage reconciliation, the emerging opportunities for oil and gas exploration in the Arctic present a potential clash between exploitation of such opportunities and the reconciliation process.

As Canada attempts to enforce policies that address the unique needs of the Arctic environment and those of the indigenous people living in the Arctic region- especially in light of Arctic oil exploration; such policies prove to be insufficient, or insufficiently implemented, and environmental injustices and grievances ensue. Apart from identifying policy gaps limiting the promotion of environmental justice for the Inuit people in the Arctic region and offering policy recommendation, the paper is also aimed at highlighting and analysing the context and issues underlying such policies.

Map of Inuit Settlement in Canada³

The Problem: Canadian Arctic oil and gas exploration in a context of environmental injustice

Studies have showed that approximately 35% of Canada's remaining marketable resources of natural gas and 37% of remaining recoverable light crude oil is in northern Canada⁴. Identified as being among the northern regions with potentials for high petroleum as well as unconventional resources are Canada's Arctic continental margin, the Arctic islands of the Northwest Territories and Nunavut, and the eastern offshore of Nunavut- regions that have been home to the Inuit people for over one-thousand years. Although, the issue of land claims for the indigenous people slowed oil exploration that had picked up in the Arctic region during the 1980s, interest for exploration in the region resumed with the settlement of claims and increased access to the Arctic due to reduced sea ice. Arctic oil and gas exploration is further encouraged by the Canadian government through its Northern Strategy.

While global warming has over the years threatened the way of life, livelihood, and the very survival of the Inuit people, the new risk of environmental degradation due to oil and gas exploration exacerbates this threat. Although Arctic exploration presents both risk and opportunity to the Inuit people, the process of distribution of risks and benefits demonstrates the extent of environmental injustice in practice and consequentially the potential for a socio-environmental conflict.

Such a potential surfaced when tension over the Arctic drilling proposal by the Imperial Oil, as a joint venture with Exxon Mobil and BP, led to protests involving the indigenous people and environmental organizations in Canada. While the fear of the risks involved with the proposed project⁵ contribute to such tension, limited engagement of the Inuit people and the mistrust that result aggravate the tension. Given that Arctic exploration is a matter of survival for the Inuit people, their meaningful involvement in such developments is crucial.

Although there are policy provision that commit companies applying for drilling authorization and exploration rights to consultation with potential affected communities, such provisions are vulnerable to manipulation. This limits not only benefits that such communities could gain from such exploration but also their voice on issues that affect them. In addition, lack of, or poor, provisions for enhancing technical skills among the Inuit significantly limits meaningful engagement. In addition, the lack of an accessible conflict management mechanism to address conflicts arising from Arctic exploration developments restricts administration of environmental justice.

While an outright socio-environmental conflict might not occur in the near future, hints of such a conflict can already be felt. For environmental justice to be fully administered in the context of Arctic exploration - at the centre of which is the welfare and engagement of the Inuit people, such policy gaps need to be addressed.

The Inuit Indigenous People in Canada

Aboriginal identities and rights have shaped the past, shape the current, and will continue to shape the future of policies of Canada. According to the 2011 National Household Survey, 1,400,685 Canadians (4.3% of the Canadian population) are of Aboriginal identity: 60.8% First Nations; 32.3% Métis; and 4.2% Inuit. Although the Inuit account for only 0.2% of the Canadian population, they account for 80.3% of the population occupying the settlement areas in the Canadian Arctic region, 40% of Canadian landmass⁶. Hence their significance in shaping policies that affect their environment - and specifically the Arctic- should not be under-estimated or undermined.

Inuit people have lived in Canada - with their communities spreading across Greenland, Alaska and Russia- since time immemorial surviving on what nature provided; from caribou, seals, walrus, narwhals to belugas which provided not only food, but also skin and sinews for clothing, ropes, and kayak covering. They have a spiritual connection to their ancestral land and their environment; and hunting, fishing and food sharing remain central to their tradition and cultural heritage. Although contact with Europeans from the fifteenth century made the Inuit in Canada increasingly dependent on western industrialized tools, clothing, and other products, their environment remained their primary means of sustenance. The Inuit also depended, and continue to depend, on hunting and fishing as a source of income for new needs such as permanent housing, health care, and education.

The policy of relocation and assimilation, and land grabs following the discovery of natural resources in the north from the 1920s to 1950s undermined the Inuit people and their way of life. The global discussions on the rights of indigenous people that led to the International Labour Organization's 1957 Indigenous and Tribal People Convention coincided with the organization of the Inuit people and lobbying to reclaim their rights and sovereignty over their ancestral lands.

Negotiations on land claims between the Canadian government and the Inuit people, resulting from the movement, began in the 1970s. These negotiations culminated in the 1975 James Bay and Northern Quebec Agreement in Nunavik; the 1984 (Western Arctic) Inuvialuit Claim Settlement Act in Inuvialuit; the 1993 Nunavut Land Claims Agreement Act in Nunavut; and the 2005 Newfoundland and Labrador Land Claim Agreement in Nunatsiavut. The four land agreements, representing 40% of the Canadian land mass, increased the autonomy of the Inuit people and control over their ancestral lands and resources therein. The Aboriginal and treaty rights (obtained through the land claim agreements) of the Inuit people as well as those of the First Nations and Métis Aboriginal people are, in addition, enshrined in the constitution of Canada⁷.

Through its Northern Strategy implemented by the Department of Aboriginal Affairs and Northern Development Canada, the Canadian government aims at promoting social and economic development and protecting the environmental heritage in the northern regions. To secure the interests of the Inuit people at a federal level and address their specific issues, the Inuit Relations Secretariat was established in 2005 within the department. However, even with settled land claims, government's public apology on relocations and increased government engagement, the Inuit's survival and way of life continues to be threatened by changes and potential changes to their environment, due to global warming and increased interests in exploration in the region.

Environmental justice predicament: Adversity and opportunity in the Arctic

The increase in Arctic temperatures, as a consequence of global warming, is estimated to be twice as much as the increase in the rest of the world⁸. With increased global warming, there is more open land and water in the Arctic resulting in the increased absorption and transfer of heat hence thereby accelerating the rate of ice melting; and the vicious cycle continues. While this has far-reaching global consequences, the indigenous people living in the Arctic region are affected directly and disproportionately.

The Arctic ecosystem is among the most fragile in the world, with little flexibility to change; where a disruption of the food web can collapse the entire web, leading even to extinction of species as is feared with the significant reduction of Ivory gull in the Canadian Arctic⁹. Due to the limited Arctic plant species, mainly lichens and mosses which are very sensitive to warming, change in plant life is having a significant impact on the animal species. Alteration of food sources and increased insect infestation threatens land animals such as the caribou. A change in their migration patterns and historical migration routes has also been observed¹⁰. The natural habitat of marine species such as polar bears, ice-dependent seals, walruses, ice algae among other species, is dwindling as sea ice reduces, changing their migration patterns, and pushing such species northwards or to extinction. The change in migration patterns, and extinction of some animal species on which the IIPCA depend for sustenance not only threaten their way of life, but also their very survival. In addition, reduction of the sea ice undermines their mobility in the Arctic for hunting purposes hence further threatening their survival.

Conversely, climate change also presents new opportunities in the Arctic region. Melting of ice has continuously increased the accessibility of resource extraction, most notably hydrocarbons. Over the years, oil companies in Canada have increasingly extended northward in their exploration and extraction. This could mean increased economic opportunity for the IIPCA as well as political empowerment through increased involvement in the developments in the Arctic. However, this also presents an additional risk to their already straining Arctic ecosystem. Drilling accidents such as blow-outs and oil spills, as experienced in oil exploration projects near marine environments, could have adverse and irreversible impact on marine life. Given the fragile nature of the Arctic ecosystem, the worst case scenario could mean an unprecedented environmental disaster and mass regional extinction of some marine species; hence significant reduction of food sources for the IIPCA.

As climate change in the Arctic presents threats and opportunities to the IIPCA, the question of how to minimize the threats and maximise on opportunities remains at the centre of the Canadian Northern Strategy. For the IIPCA, their survival, traditions, and culture remain central in their engagement on northern development. Despite increased engagement of the IIPCA in the discussions on issues around environmental changes and oil exploration in the Arctic, such engagements remains wanting given how much the IIPCA stands to lose. The historical experiences of the Inuit in Canada, and the legacy of that history, makes engagement on the fate of the Arctic expressly sensitive: as this fate exhibits a quintessential example of the disproportionate distribution of threats and opportunities; and in this engagement, un-balanced power relations and cultural bias.

The national policy outlook

Canada's Northern Strategy is based on four priority areas: exercising Arctic sovereignty; protecting environmental heritage; promoting social and economic development; and improving and devolving Northern governance. Social and economic development agenda which is based on exploring opportunities in the North, most importantly Arctic natural resource base, couples with the agenda on environmental protection to form a basis for the policy outlook on oil exploration in the Arctic.

The outlook on Canadian policy on oil exploration in the Arctic revolve around, inter alia, the Canada Oil and Gas Operations Act, Canada Oil and Gas Drilling and Production Regulations, Canada Petroleum Resources Act, Canadian Environmental Assessment Act; Environmental Protection Plan Guidelines; and more specific to the Arctic, the Arctic Water Pollution Prevention Act, Canada Shipping Act, Fisheries Act, Oceans Act, Nunavut Land Claims Agreement and Act, Inuvialuit Final Agreement. The National Energy Board (hereinafter, NEB), Canada's energy and safety regulator, following increased interest in Arctic oil exploration, published Filing Requirements for Offshore Drilling in the Canadian Arctic (2014) after a consultative review conference with indigenous peoples' organizations and governments, oil companies, scholars, and other experts.

These filing requirements essentially incorporate the laws, policies, and guidelines that the NEB refer to in reviewing applications for drilling authorization in the Arctic region. Required from an oil company in the application for drilling authorization is an Environmental Protection Plan, a Safety Plan, a Contingency Plan in case of drilling accident, and an Emergency Response Plan among other documents. In addition, the company needs to demonstrate that it has consulted with communities that would potentially be affected by the project. It needs to present its consultation approach, policy, and goals; if established, a consultation protocol; a list of government authorities included in consultation, including Aboriginal officials; a list of identified groups and people to be potentially affected, a summary of their concerns and response to raise concerns; measures to be taken to address the concerns; and documentation of the influence of the consultations on the project.

In addition to the regulatory authorization, an applicant company is also required to apply for an Exploration License with the Department of Aboriginal Affairs and Northern Development Canada (hereinafter, AANDC) through a right issuance process; for land, even that below the ocean. As part of the right issuance application, a Benefits Plan is also submitted; and is reviewed by the Minister of Aboriginal Affairs and Northern Development.

The Benefit Plan provision in the Canada Oil and Gas Operation Act commits applicant companies to affirmation programs to ensure that the disadvantaged people are offered access to training and employment opportunities. The Act stipulates that companies should develop such a plan in consultation with potentially affected communities. The AANDC also monitors the benefit plans and the reviews annual Report on the Implementation of the Plan. The department also recommends the development and implementation of training and employment strategies as well as business and procurement processes guidelines to maximise Northern benefits, with a priority to the Aboriginal population.

With the new filing requirements, oil companies will bear absolute liability for oil spills and blow-outs and hence need to demonstrate their ability to bear this liability before their drilling application is authorised. When enforced, the Energy Safety and Security Act (February, 2015) will allow operationalization of the amendments on liability and financial assurance provisions of the Canada Oil and Gas Operations Act from the 1987 upper cap of \$40 million cap to \$1 billion. While these policy provisions have been described as forward looking¹¹, there are a number of identified gaps, especially as it relates to the IIPCA engagement.

Identified Policy Needs and Gaps

- Although the filing requirements emphasises the need for consultation between applicant companies and potential affected communities, the consultation process is left at the discretion of oil companies hence making the process vulnerable to manipulation. There is no provision for enhanced monitoring of such consultations beyond the paper-evidence provided during the application for drilling authorization. The Canada Oil and Gas Operation Act stipulates that ‘the extent of communication during the development of a Benefits Plan will depend on the nature and scope of the oil and gas work or activity’. This provision increases opportunity for manipulation.
- The consultation provisions also do not address the need for empowerment to ensure meaningful consultation on technical issues referred to in the Contingency, Safety, Environmental Protection, and Emergency Response plans. Although the Canadian government has increasingly involved the Inuit people in technical discussions such as during Canada Program for International Polar Year events, technical knowledge that would enable of meaningful engagement in evaluation of drilling applications remain limited¹².
- Despite the Benefit Plan Guidelines for the North indicating the need for prioritizing the indigenous people in benefits emanating from the projects, the training of indigenous people is observed to be limited towards low-end jobs¹³. Apart from significantly limiting the potential benefits accrued to the IIPCA from such projects, it also limits the future growth of Inuit employees beyond the lifetime of specific projects and consequently the learning process on oil exploration in general.
- A clear conflict management mechanism accessible to the IIPCA on issues specific to Arctic explorations has not yet been established. This policy requirement is based on the acknowledgement that new developments, especially those that can endanger survival and of which the IIPCA have little knowledge about, can cause conflict between the IIPCA, and oil companies and the government. The hearing process provided for by the NEB has so far been dominated by hearings on construction and operationalization of pipelines; and is not easily accessible to the IIPCA even with the provision of financial support for participants’ travel costs.
- While devastation of the environment to the to the Inuit’s way of life and culture- which are intrinsically linked- cannot be monetized, such an evaluation calls for a consultative approach and understanding. Although the absolute liability will potentially be increased to \$1 billion, research on the financial costs resulting to a worst case scenario environmental disaster in the remote Arctic has been limited. As oil exploration projects in the Inuit Inuvialuit Settlement Areas are subject to the Inuvialuit Final Agreement, absolute liability would include a reimbursement for present and future loss of wildlife harvest which could translate to reimbursing generations in the worst case scenario. Even without such requirements, the 1989 Exxon Valdez spill in Alaska costed \$2.5 billion for clean-up alone; total cost including compensation is estimated at \$7 billion¹⁴.

Policy Option: Enhancing the environmental justice outlook

Although the term ‘environmental justice’ is not a commonly used phrase in Canada’s discussions and policies on environmental protection in the Arctic, Canada has reaffirmed and continue to reaffirm its underlying principles through discussions and policies- albeit with limitations. The term environmental justice has been defined, and expounded on, within the lines of fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies¹⁵. Although the focus of environmental justice has been on the distributive dimension, ‘justice-as-recognition’ has been noted to be promising in resolving tensions resulting from varying social and ecological values¹⁶. Both dimensions are related to the concept of procedural justice, which is concerned with the process of a decision making process in achieving environmental justice¹⁷.

Canada’s policies on Arctic exploration have focussed to a larger extent on the distributive dimension- benefit and burden sharing- and fallen short to a greater extent on the recognition and procedural dimensions. Where the procedural dimension has been invoked, this has fallen short on the recognition dimension by not adequately acknowledging cultural difference in engagement mechanisms.

Policy recommendations

- ***Monitoring mechanisms***

To ensure that applicant companies collaborate, with the potentially affected IIPCA, in preparation of their application for drilling authorisation as well as exploration rights, there is need for enhanced monitoring mechanisms. While such mechanisms would be better overseen by the NEB and the AANDC, as it relates to drilling authorization and exploration rights respectively, a monitoring strategy that involves IIPCA organizations would be ideal. In this way, monitoring consultations made at the grass-root level would be possible. Such a strategy should also include consequences of not adhering to the consultation provisions of the filing requirements and the benefit plan provisions.

- ***Community level engagement***

Developing a community engagement strategy for the IIPCA aimed at empowering communities as opposed to limiting engagement with Inuit government and organisations representatives would great a broader awareness and understanding hence reduce tensions at community level. Such a strategy could be developed in collaboration- with the NEB, the AANDC’s Inuit Relations Secretariat, Inuit government and organizations representatives, and the Inuit communities residing in the Arctic. Policy actions to be considered could include community hearings; and issues subject to engagement could include environmental assessment strategy specific to the Arctic eco-system, and risk prevention and management. Instead of the representative of IIPCA going to the mainstream Canada for engagement opportunities, such opportunities need to be availed in the Arctic region. While community engagement on technical issues may not be feasible at the onset, the recognition of the people and their concerns would create more opportunity for engagement and work towards bridging the value differences of western development ideals and that of the Inuit population.

- ***Development of technical skills among the IIPCA and engagement in technical research***

The Environmental Studies Research Fund (ESRF), established under the Canada Petroleum Resources Act, should be optimised for engagement in collaborative research on the socio-environmental impacts of potential oil and gas explorations in the Arctic. The focus of this

collaboration being an exchange of the Inuit traditional knowledge of the environment and the modern scientific and technical research models. Such an exchange will hence allow for a broader understanding of issues at stakes for all involved stakeholders and reduce future conflicts with regards to the environmental aspect of rights issuance. Consequently, this will empower the IIPCA to participate in a critical and informed review of Contingency, Safety, Environmental Protection, and Emergency Response plans issued by applicant oil companies for drilling authorizations. In addition, collaborative research need to be done on the environmental, social and financial implications of a worst case scenario of an exploration accident in the Arctic.

- ***Securing training, job and business opportunity***

The Inuit Relations Secretariat, whose mandate includes representing Inuit interests in federal policy negotiations, should take the lead in ensuring that IIPCA benefit from opportunities emanating from exploration activities. A scholarship program specific for IIPCA students interested in study programs on petroleum and resource management and environmental assessment, among others related to oil exploration could ensure that more Inuit gain technical skills to be actively engaged in future exploration activities. In the review of the benefits plan submitted for issuance of exploration licenses, the secretariat should ensure that benefits would lead to long-term development for the IIPCA. Training and job opportunities for the Inuit should also be availed at high-end jobs, even where further training is required. In addition, business opportunities should, to the extent possible, be limited to local providers.

- ***Conflict management mechanism and mainstreaming cultural difference***

To efficiently and effectively prevent, manage and resolve conflict emanating from Arctic exploration activities, there is need for a mechanism to ensure such conflicts are addressed. While the NEB provides a public hearing framework, such a framework could be adapted to the needs and culture of the IIPCA. In addition, such hearings should be accessible to the IIPCA public and could be complemented by community mechanisms where possible and/or necessary.

- ***Positive engagement of the civil society and the media***

The civil society and the media could play positive and meaningful role in bringing issues related to Arctic development to the public, including the IIPCA. Enhanced engagement of NGO with IIPCA in programs advocating for environmental justice in the Arctic would enhance the voice of the Inuit people on issues that affect them. Although the IIPCA are organized in regional organizations, partnership with experienced NGOs such as Ecojust, WWF, and Greenpeace, among others, would enhance their advocacy capability and would act as a check to corporate practice and government engagement.

Conclusion

The misfortune of the Arctic due to global warming is intertwined with opportunities for the Inuit indigenous people living in the Canadian Arctic region (IIPCA). Apart from the potential economic benefits that will emanate from oil and gas exploration, there are political and social implications where empowerment due to meaningful engagement is anticipated. Engagement is especially necessary for the Inuit people since there are risks involved; risks that could threaten their very survival. However, as the paper demonstrates, for such benefits to be realized there is a need to consider and reconsider related policy provisions.

Although the government, aligned to the Northern Strategy, has increasingly encouraged engagement of the IIPCA there are some policy gaps that could be addressed to better realize this commitment. The paper proposes a policy approach that provides for a broader implementation of environmental justice; where not only the distributive dimension but also the procedural and recognition dimensions are realized. In enhancing engagement, recognition of the Inuit culture and value system is necessary and this is only possible when structural constraints and inequalities are addressed.

In improving the practice of environmental justice in the Arctic, the paper proposes: enhanced monitoring of policies that provide for engagement; a mechanism for community level engagement; development of technical skills among the Inuit and collaborative research; proactive enhancements to ensure the IIPCA benefit from exploration activities; conflict management mechanisms that mainstream Inuit culture; and positive engagement of civil society and the media. While more research on the governance mechanism in the Arctic settlement areas is required to ensure proper implementation of the recommendations, the recommendations offer a promising policy framework for addressing policy gaps limiting the (present and future) realization of environmental justice.

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¹ The victimization of the indigenous people is acknowledged in the preamble of the 2007 UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.

² See Baron, A. (2014, pp. 9-12) on the debates around the definition of indigenous people.

³ Department of Aboriginal Affairs and Northern Development. Government of Canada. Retrieved from <https://www.aadnc-aandc.gc.ca/eng/1100100016900/1100100016908> on 16 August 2015.

⁴ National Energy Board. Canada's Energy Futures, 2011

⁵ See the interactive map on impact scenarios in case of oil spills in the Beaufort Sea. Exploring the Risks by the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) <http://arcticspills.wwf.ca/#scenario/es-berge/es-berge-d/time/734877/> Retrieved on 16 August, 2015.

⁶ Aboriginal Peoples in Canada: First Nations People, Metis, and Inuit. Analytical document. Statistics Canada. National Household Survey. 2011. Government of Canada.

⁷ Constitution Act, 1982. Schedule B. Part II Par. 5. Government of Canada.

⁸ ACIA. (2004). Impacts of Global Warming: Arctic Climate Impact Assessment. Cambridge University Press. p. 10 on Key Findings.

⁹ Ivory Gull. Species at Risk Public Registry. Government of Canada. Retrieved from http://www.sararegistry.gc.ca/species/speciesDetails_e.cfm?sid=50 on 23 August 2015.

¹⁰ ACIA. (2004, pp. 10-11). Also see Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). 2007. Climate Change 2007: Synthesis report. Summary for Policymakers. An assessment of the IPCC on climate change. pp. 3,12

¹¹ Pembiana Institute, Ecojustice, and World Wildlife Fund (WWF), although cautious about Arctic oil exploration, admit that Canadian policy and the recent Filing Requirements would reduce risks involved with the exercise. <http://www.wwf.ca/?10222/wwf-and-ecojustice-welcome-neb-arctic-offshore-drilling-report> WWF and Ecojustice welcome NEB Arctic offshore drilling report Dec.2011

¹² The gap in technical knowledge on issues around oil exploration assessment is assessed on analysis of discussion during the 2011NEB conference on filing requirements. See National Energy Board (NEB). 2011. Arctic Offshore Drilling review- list of participants and comments. While this is just one indicator, the limited opportunity of higher education due to the poverty levels and isolation of the Arctic community is another.

¹³ The issue was raised by the director of the Ulukhaktot Community Corporation during the 2011NEB conference on filing requirements. See National Energy Board. December, 2011 p.18

¹⁴ Susan Lyon & Daniel Weiss. 30 April, 2010. The devastating consequences of Exxon Valdez and BP Gulf. Center for American Progress. Retrieved from <https://www.americanprogress.org/issues/green/news/2010/04/30/7620/oil-spills-by-the-numbers/> on 23 August 2015.

¹⁵ U.S.A. Environmental Protection Agency. See <http://www.epa.gov/environmentaljustice/> for the agency's definition and related policy papers.

¹⁶ Martin, A., Mcguire, S., & Sullivan, S. (2013)

¹⁷ Martin, A. (2013)